

Administrative coercion and administrative penalties in the irration under the legislation of Ukraine

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Objective. The purpose of this article is to explore approaches to defining the legal nature of administrative coercion and administrative penalties, their correlation, and interdependence in the process of practical implementation by law enforcement agencies (officials).

The methodological basis of the article comprises a set of scientific cognition methods: dialectical, structural-functional analysis, formal-normative analysis, comparative-legal, phenomenological, and logical methods.

Key words: administrative coercion, administrative penalties, public administration, administrative sanctions, administrative offenses, authorized bodies (officials), administrative delictology.

Results. The study attempts a comprehensive analysis of the correlation between administrative coercion and administrative pen-

alties, considering accumulated theoretical and practical experience. The aim is to develop a new perspective on their role in law enforcement and legal practice and to explore ways to improve these institutions.

Annotation. During the formation of a legal state, significant importance is attributed to such institutions of administrative law as administrative coercion and administrative delictology. The concept of administrative reform in Ukraine, along with other measures, includes the reform of administrative legislation in general, as well as the institutions of administrative coercion and administrative liability, with administrative penalties occupying a prominent place among them.

The relevance of issues surrounding administrative coercion and administrative penalties is based on the following factors: 1) Economic factor – The establishment of a market economy necessitates state regulation of economic relations through specific legal means. At the same time, the scope of these means, the grounds for their application, and their types must be defined at the legislative level; 2) Political factor – There is a need to establish and maintain a regime of legality in the sphere of executive power to ensure conditions for the proper realization of human and citizen rights and freedoms in administrative-legal relations; 3) Normative-Legal factor – The development of new and the reform of existing administrative legislation in Ukraine should be based on scientifically grounded consideration of ongoing social, economic, and political changes to create an effective legal mechanism for protecting social relations.

Although the issues of administrative coercion and administrative penalties are central to the context of maintaining public order, protecting citizens' rights and freedoms, and preventing offenses, they have not been studied independently of other legal phenomena. Traditional approaches and principles have remained unchanged for a long time, which has negatively impacted lawmaking.

Various aspects of the interaction between administrative coercion and administrative penalties have been analyzed to varying degrees in the works of Ukrainian scholars in the field of administrative law, including V.B. Averyanov, O.F. Andriyko, H.P. Bondarenko, Yu.P. Bytiak, S.T. Honcharuk, I.P. Holosnichenko, Ye.V. Dodin, S.V. Kivalov, L.V. Koval, Ye.B. Kubko, A.T. Komzyuk, D.M. Lukianets, I.V. Martyanov, V.F. Opryshko, I.M. Pakhomov, I.A. Tymchenko, V.V. Tsvetkov, Yu.S. Shemshuchenko, V.I. Shyshkin, O.M. Yakuba, and others.

At the same time, it should be noted that when administrative penalties were addressed at the doctrinal level, research was most often conducted within the framework of existing legislation, which currently does not adequately meet the requirements of reforming Ukrainian administrative law or its harmonization with European legal standards.

Scientific research has not been sufficiently directed toward a conceptual understanding of trends in legal changes, new phenomena in lawmaking, and law enforcement practices. The essence of administrative coercion and administrative penalties, their distinctive features, functions, and purposes, require more thorough examination and study to distinguish them from other forms of state coercive measures.

Defining the legal concepts of administrative coercion and administrative penalties, along with a list of their characteristics, will

make it possible to resolve any contentious issues through analysis, comparison, and correlation, thereby clarifying the legal phenomenon in question, the legal institution it belongs to, and the applicable rules for its implementation.

Presentation of the main material. It is clear that measures of administrative coercion are applied by authorized state bodies in an established form and in compliance with legally prescribed procedures. These measures entail moral and material consequences for individuals (both natural and legal persons) who find themselves in conflict with the law.

At the same time, legal doctrine has not offered a unified definition of administrative coercion or clarified its legal nature. Legal nature refers to the identification of phenomena within the framework of law and the means of their emergence in objective reality. For legal phenomena, uncovering their legal nature implies determining their genetic origins, classifying them within a specific legal category, and linking them to a particular element of law [1, p. 14]. One can agree with the assertion that one of the main functions of administrative coercion is law enforcement. This means that the law grants authorized bodies (officials), acting on behalf of the state and within their competencies, the right to perform necessary actions aimed at preventing and suppressing offenses. One can also concur that administrative coercion manifests as psychological or physiological influence exerted by state bodies and public associations on individuals to compel them to comply with legal norms [2, p. 5]. However, it should be noted that public associations can apply coercive measures only when they are granted corresponding authority by the state, which may be regarded as a form of public oversight. This is one of the key factors in resolving societal disputes since it regulates

and consolidates the activities of all social actors [3, p. 7].

An important factor is that administrative coercion differs from civil, criminal, and disciplinary coercion as an independent type of coercion because it possesses its own distinct characteristics.

Firstly, the main purpose of administrative coercion is the protection of social relations that are formed and operate mainly in the sphere of public administration. At the same time, the scope of social relations protected by administrative coercion is not limited to administrative relations alone.

Measures of administrative coercion are employed in the implementation of executive power by relevant bodies and officials, which is, in turn, a manifestation of state-authority powers. Thus, all measures of administrative coercion are characterized by a state-authoritarian nature. Scholars, discussing the peculiarities of administrative coercion, note that it manifests in state-legal physical and psychological influence on individuals' consciousness and behavior in the form of personal, organizational, or property restrictions, leading to certain adverse consequences [4, p. 94]. For instance, personal restrictions can be implemented during the administrative detention of an offender under Article 260 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses (CUAO), or during their delivery to law enforcement agencies to draft a protocol on an administrative offense (Article 259 of the CUAO). Organizational restrictions may include the suspension of a business's activities due to non-compliance with fire safety regulations. Property restrictions include fines, confiscation, and paid seizure of property imposed through administrative procedures.

Secondly, a characteristic feature of administrative coercion is its establishment in

legislative acts, granting the right to apply coercive measures to authorized bodies (officials). Typically, these include executive authorities and their officials authorized to perform law enforcement functions in the sphere of public administration. The wide range of subjects authorized to apply administrative coercion is due to the specific nature of administrative relations, which often require the rapid application of these measures. This feature underscores that administrative coercion is indeed being applied.

Thirdly, another distinguishing feature of administrative coercion is the legal basis for its application. Unlike other forms of state coercion – criminal, civil, or disciplinary – the application of administrative coercion is not limited to the commission of an offense. The grounds for applying such measures are much broader and more diverse.

For example, under Ukrainian legislation, certain conditions such as epidemics, natural disasters, epizootics, technogenic catastrophes, and other emergencies may justify the use of administrative coercion in the absence of an offense or culpability, aiming to prevent adverse consequences and mitigate their impact [5].

Considering the above, administrative coercion can be understood as an administrative-legal mechanism for protecting and safeguarding specific social relations, which has its inherent components. These include:

a) Legal grounds, forms, methods, and sanctions aimed at preventing offenses and protecting social relations from unlawful encroachments;

b) Legislative support for the activities of authorized bodies in applying c) Legal regulation of the system of bodies responsible for protecting legal relations from unlawful encroachments.

Administrative coercion is implemented through: a) The application of administrative sanctions—administrative penalties prescribed by the CUAO and other laws; b) The application of other sanctions for administrative offenses that do not entail administrative liability. For example, measures for influencing minors aged 16 to 18 for committing administrative offenses:

- 1) A public or other form of apology to the victim;
- 2) Warnings;
- 3) Reprimands or severe reprimands;
- 4) Assigning minors to the supervision of parents or guardians, educational or labor collectives (with their consent), or certain individuals upon their request (Article 24-1 of the CUAO).

c) The application of other coercive measures that are not enforced through sanctions and do not entail administrative liability, such as document checks, restricting entry to specific areas, or suspension of driving privileges.

The fundamental expression of administrative coercion should be considered administrative sanctions, which, in our opinion, represent the most effective form of response by authorized state bodies (officials) to violations of legislation on its territory.

In terms of content and purpose, sanctions are expressed in:

- a) Prohibitions, demands, and restrictions that affect the freedom of individuals—both physical and legal;
- b) Denials of the right to protection—such as the granting of licenses, powers, exemption from taxes, granting immunity, etc.;
- c) Imposition of fines;
- d) Seizure, confiscation of money and other property, and denial of rights to them;
- e) Compensation, restitution, reimbursement of expenses, or damages;

- f) Cancellation or suspension of licenses;
- g) Implementation of other coercive or restrictive measures.

A sanction, as a negative reaction by the state to a violation of a legal norm, arises only in the presence of unlawful behavior or improper fulfillment of generally established rules.

Considering the above, one can define the place of administrative penalties within the structure of administrative sanctions and administrative coercion.

The issue of administrative penalties in legal literature is more often studied not as an independent legal phenomenon but in the process of analyzing the institution of administrative delictology. This approach is explained by the specific relationship and interdependence of these legal phenomena, but it significantly narrows the study of the direct issues of administrative penalties.

At one time, a number of scholars—administrativists—paid attention to the issue of administrative penalties in various parameters: in the context of characterizing specific types of penalties, in the context of administrative responsibility, or regarding the application of penalties by certain authorized bodies (officials) for specific offenses.

An analysis of scientific research related to penalties allows us to pay attention to the following approaches to this issue: a) In the institutional paradigm, as an element of the institution of administrative responsibility; b) In the normative-structural paradigm, as an element of the structure of the legal norm; c) In the paradigm of state coercion, as a type of administrative-legal sanction.

In the institutional context, a penalty is an element that is "integrated" into the system of legal norms, the interaction of which, in turn, forms the institution of administrative responsibility.

In formulating an approach to legal responsibility as a system of legal norms, it is necessary to note that administrative responsibility combines two groups of norms. First, there are material norms that establish the foundations—defining types of administrative offenses, penalties, and subjects of responsibility. Second, there are procedural norms that form the mechanism of administrative proceedings in cases of administrative offenses (misdemeanors).

In the normative-structural understanding, administrative penalties can be seen as one of the types of administrative-legal sanctions, which is a form of state coercion in a broad sense. Considering the sectoral nature of legal regulation, it is more accurate to talk about administrative coercion in a narrow sense.

In the context of administrative-legal sanctions, we should refer to this legal category as part of criminal sanctions.

The consideration of administrative penalties solely through the prism of administrative responsibility has led to some one-sidedness in their definition as a legal category. For instance, S.T. Honcharuk defines a penalty as "a materialized expression of administrative responsibility, a negative legal consequence of illegal behavior by a person who must answer for their unlawful act and bear the corresponding punishment in the form of certain unfavorable measures of moral, material, and physical influence—it is the last link in the system of administrative coercion measures. They are a measure of responsibility" [9, p. 23].

However, administrative penalties stand out among these measures. They are characterized by a state-coercive nature. Certainly, they also have an educational character, but their essence lies in the state's coercive influence on offenders. In other words, authorized

bodies (officials) perform law enforcement functions and control compliance with legislation by the subjects of legal relations. In fact, these relations are of an authoritative-coercive nature, with no subordination of a service character.

Administrative penalties combine elements of a punitive, educational, and preventive nature, which, in principle, is defined by the Code of Administrative Offenses (Article 23). It is also worth noting that the law enforcement potential of administrative penalties ensures the protection of other legal norms and legal relations.

A particular feature of administrative penalties is that their application is mostly extrajudicial. Compared to criminal coercion sanctions, the application of administrative penalties is assigned to a large number of executive authorities (officials). However, along with this, the legislator has singled out specific administrative penalties that can only be applied through judicial procedures. According to the Code of Administrative Offenses, out of the ten penalties it provides for, eight fall under the jurisdiction of the court (judge)—these include monetary confiscation of items used as tools or direct objects of the administrative offense, confiscation of such items, deprivation of the right to hold certain positions or engage in specific activities, community service, corrective labor, socially useful work, administrative arrest, and detention in a guardhouse (Articles 28, 29, 30, 30-1, 31, 31-1, 32).

The purpose of applying administrative penalties also has its own peculiarities. While civil-legal sanctions primarily aim at compensation for harm caused by improper fulfillment of obligations or committing other unlawful acts, the goal of an administrative penalty is to punish the offender for the committed offense, as well as to prevent future

offenses, primarily for those individuals upon whom administrative penalties (both main and additional) are imposed according to the law.

It should be noted that when applying administrative penalties that cannot compensate for the state's moral damages, the main goal is punishment. Thus, administrative penalties consist of restricting or depriving individuals of subjective rights and benefits. The voluntary fulfillment of the penalty imposed on the offender does not alter its coercive nature because, in the case of non-fulfillment of the imposed obligation, the state, represented by authorized bodies (officials), reserves the right to apply other coercive measures to ensure proper compliance, such as the compulsory collection of unpaid fines from the offender's income—salary, scholarship, pension, etc.

The application of administrative penalties is formalized by the authorized body in a special individual act. The application of an administrative penalty results in the individual being in a "state of administrative liability." This legal position is crucial when imposing an administrative penalty in the case of repeated, recurrent, or systematic violations of legal norms within one year, as an aggravating circumstance.

Thus, the grounds for applying administrative penalties are much broader and not limited to non-compliance with or violation of prohibitions; they can also be applied in cases of improper fulfillment of legislatively defined duties.

Conclusions. Administrative coercion, unlike other forms of social (public) regulation, has distinct features that set it apart. It possesses a complex legal nature. On the one hand, it ensures compliance with and proper execution of legal norms, while on the other hand, it is

based on and implemented through a legal norm.

Administrative coercion serves as an independent method of state influence on the subjects of public relations, alongside persuasion and encouragement. It is aimed at protecting established legal relationships and ensuring the strict and accurate implementation of legal norms. The differences between sectoral norms and the degree of social danger posed by sectoral delicts determine the unique characteristics of state coercive measures.

Administrative penalties are one type of administrative-legal sanction. At the same time, they possess certain common features that distinguish them from others. First, they are provided for by a specific legal norm, the non-compliance or violation of which serves as the basis for their application. Second, the primary function of administrative penalties is to punish the offender and prevent further offenses. Third, this punishment is implemented through the institution of administrative responsibility, of which it is an integral part. Fourth, the law establishes a special procedure for their application. Fifth, they are applied by specially authorized bodies (officials) within their legally defined competence.

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Ukrayna qanunvericiliyinə uyğun olmayan inzibati məcburiyyət və inzibati cəzalar

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Hüquqi dövlətin formalaşması zamanı inzibati hüquq institutlarına inzibati məcburiyyət və inzibati deliktologiya kimi mühüm əhəmiyyət verilir. Ukraynada inzibati islahat konsepsiyası digər tədbirlərlə yanaşı ümumilikdə inzibati qanunvericiliyin, habelə inzibati məcburiyyət və inzibati məsuliyyət institutlarının islahatını ehtiva edir ki, bunlar arasında inzibati cəzalar mühüm yer tutur.

Açar sözlər: inzibati məcburiyyət, inzibati cəzalar, dövlət idarəetməsi, inzibati tənbehlər, inzibati xətalər, səlahiyyətli orqanlar (vəzifəli şəxslər), inzibati deliktologiya.

Ukrayna mevzuatına görə idari zorlama ve idari cezalar

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Hukuk devletinin oluşumu sırasında, idari zorlama ve idari suç bilimi gibi idari hukuk kurumlarına önemli bir önem atfedilir. Ukrayna'daki idari reform kavramı, diğer önlemlerle birlikte, genel olarak idari mevzuatın reformunu ve idari zorlama ve idari sorumluluk kurumlarını içerir; idari cezalar bunların arasında önemli bir yer tutar.

Anahtar sözcükler: idari zorlama, idari cezalar, kamu yönetimi, idari yaptırımlar, idari suçlar, yetkili organlar (görevliler), idari suç bilimi.

